

Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Catalysis in Bromamine-T Oxidation of Propanaldehyde and Butanaldehyde in Acidic Media

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Manuscript received 16 February 1990, revised 16 August 1991, accepted 3 September 1991

Kinetics of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of propanaldehyde and butanaldehyde by acidic solution of bromamine-T have been investigated. The results show that oxidation of both the aldehydes follows first order kinetics in bromamine-T both aldehydes, hydrogen ion concentration and Ru^{III}. Decreasing effect of [chloride ion] variation on reaction rate was observed. No effect of *p*-toluene sulphonamide and ionic strength of the medium was observed. Activation parameters have been evaluated. A suitable mechanism in conformity with the results has been proposed.

BROMAMINE-T (BAT) is a potent oxidising agent and has been used in the estimation of several organic compounds¹. Some investigations involving oxidation of alcohols² by acidic solution of bromamine-T (BAT) in presence of Ru^{III} as catalyst have been reported. Present paper reports the kinetics and mechanism of Ru^{III} catalysed oxidation of propanaldehyde and butanaldehyde in perchloric acid solutions.

Experimental

The aldehydes, chloramine-T and perchloric acid (all E. Merck), *p*-toluene sulphonamide (Kochlight), ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Mathey) and other reagents (AnalaR) were used. Bromamine-T solution was prepared and standardised^{1,2}. The reaction stills were blackened from outside. Double-distilled water was used throughout the investigation. Deuterium oxide (purity 99%) was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay. Calculated amount of bromamine-T was added to the already equilibrated mixture containing substrate, perchloric acid, ruthenium(III) chloride and potassium chloride solution to initiate the reaction. The kinetics of reaction was followed iodometrically by examining aliquots of the mixture for bromamine-T at different time intervals.

Results and Discussion

The values of first order rate constants (Table 1) at several initial concentrations of bromamine-T and both the substrates indicate first-order dependence of the reactions on bromamine-T as well as on

both the aldehydes. The average values of second order rate constants ($k_2 = k_1/[\text{substrate}]$) have been calculated as 5.38 ± 0.04 and $5.85 \pm 0.07 \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of propanaldehyde and butanaldehyde respectively, at conditions stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [REACTANTS] ON REACTION VELOCITY

[HClO₄] = $1.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, [Ru^{III} chloride] = $4.4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$,
[Cl⁻] = $5.00 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, Temp. = 35°

[Bromamine-T] $\times 10^3/\text{M}$	[Aldehyde] $\times 10^3/\text{M}$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Paopanal	Butanal
0.25	2.00	10.76	11.86
0.50	2.00	10.84	11.78
0.75	2.00	10.75	11.76
1.00	2.00	10.80	11.80
1.25	2.00	10.78	11.82
1.67	2.00	10.77	11.78
2.00	2.00	10.80	11.79
2.50	2.00	10.80	11.78
2.00	2.00	10.80	11.79
2.00	2.50	13.44	14.85
2.00	5.00	26.81	29.50
2.00	7.50	39.53	44.40
2.00	10.00	54.70	56.70
2.00	15.00	81.16	87.64
2.00	20.00	108.20	115.80

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the rate of oxidation of the substrates was studied under the conditions as indicated in Table 2. The data indicate linear relationship between k_1 values and [H⁺] showing first order kinetics in [H⁺]. The result obtained at various concentrations of ruthenium(III) (Table 3) shows first order dependence of the reactions on ruthenium(III) which was obvious from the

direct proportionality between k_1 values and ruthenium(III) concentration.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$

[Bromamine-T] = 2.00×10^{-3} M, [Aldehyde] = 1.00×10^{-3} M,
[Ru^{III} chloride] = 4.4×10^{-7} M, $[Cl^-]$ = 5.00×10^{-3} M,

Temp. = 35°

[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ /M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	Propanal	Butanal
1.00	5.42	5.86
1.28	6.95	7.51
1.60	8.66	9.38
2.00	10.82	11.72
2.50	13.57	14.66
4.00	21.66	23.46
5.00	27.18	29.30

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [Ru^{III} chloride]

[Bromamine-T] = 2.00×10^{-3} M, [Aldehyde] = 1.00×10^{-3} M,
[HClO₄] = 1.00×10^{-3} M, $[Cl^-]$ = 5.00×10^{-3} M, Temp. = 35°

[Ru ^{III} chloride] × 10 ⁶ /M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	Propanal	Butanal
0.44	5.42	5.86
0.88	10.82	11.73
1.32	16.24	17.58
1.76	21.62	23.48
2.20	27.12	29.30
2.64	32.54	35.14

Insignificant effect of *p*-toluene sulphonamide (one of the reaction product), negligible effect of ionic strength of the medium (affected by the addition of various amounts of NaClO₄) and marked effect due to chloride ion variation was observed (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF TEMPERATURE, IONIC STRENGTH OF MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF CHLORIDE AND *p*-TOLUENE SULPHONAMIDE

[Bromamine-T] = 2.00×10^{-3} M, [HClO₄] = 1.00×10^{-3} M,
[Ru^{III} chloride] = 4.4×10^{-7} M,
[Propanal] = [Butanal] = 2.00×10^{-3} M

Temp. °C	Ionic strength M	[Cl ⁻] M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
			Propanal	Butanal
30	0.08	0.05	7.77	8.62
35	0.08	0.05	10.80	11.80
40	0.08	0.05	14.10	16.12
45	0.08	0.05	21.57	22.40
35	0.09	0.05	10.80	11.80
35	0.10	0.05	10.79	11.79
35	0.15	0.05	10.80	11.78
35	0.25	0.05	10.78	11.77
35	0.50	0.05	10.80	11.79
35	0.08	0.05 ^a	32.41	39.36
35	0.08	0.10 ^a	17.04	22.24
35	0.08	0.20 ^a	10.80	12.73
35	0.08	0.30 ^a	8.57	9.80
35	0.08	0.50 ^a	7.13	8.08
35 ^b	0.08	0.05	10.80	11.80
35 ^c	0.08	0.05	10.78	11.79
35 ^d	0.08	0.05	10.80	11.78
35 ^e	0.08	0.05	10.80	11.77

^a[HClO₄] = 1.00×10^{-3} M and [Ru^{III} chloride] = 2.64×10^{-6} M.

^b[CH₃C₆H₄SO₂NH₂] = 1.00×10^{-3} M. ^c[CH₃C₆H₄SO₂NH₂] = 1.25×10^{-3} M.

^d[CH₃C₆H₄SO₂NH₂] = 1.50×10^{-3} M.

^e[CH₃C₆H₄SO₂NH₂] = 2.00×10^{-3} M.

The kinetic data obtained at 30, 35, 40 and 45° are given in Table 4. The values of energy of activation (E_a) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) were found to be 53.8 kJ mol⁻¹ and -19.5 e.u. respectively (propanaldehyde) and 49.4 kJ mol⁻¹ and -22.7 e.u. respectively (butanaldehyde).

Stoichiometry and product analysis: Various sets of experiments were carried out by varying bromamine-T and aldehyde ratio. The excess bromamine-T left over in each set was estimated. The studies show that one mole of aldehyde consumed one mole of bromamine-T and accordingly the following stoichiometric equation could be formulated where R represents CH₃C₆H₄SO₂ and R' represents C₂H₅ (in propanaldehyde) and C₃H₇ (in butanaldehyde) respectively,

Propionic and butyric acids were identified as one of the end-products respectively, by chromatographic technique.

Ru^{III} chloride in hydrochloric acid forms [RuCl₆]³⁻ which is in equilibrium with [RuCl₅(H₂O)]²⁻ as given below³,

In acidic medium, equilibrium (2) in the right direction would be highly favoured suggesting [RuCl₅(H₂O)]²⁻ as the principal reactive species⁴. In acidic medium bromamine-T would give *p*-toluene sulphonamide (BAT'),

BAT would also produce dibromo-*p*-toluensulphonamide (DBT) and free sulphonamide⁵,

Thus we have three oxidising species of bromamine-T, viz. BAT, BAT' and DBT. When either BAT or DBT is assumed as the actual species, the rate law deduced does not explain our observed kinetics and hence either of them can not be assumed as the real oxidising species. Hence BAT' is the only choice which can be assumed as actual oxidising species in our case. Similar species of chloramine-T have also been reported in acidic medium where H⁺ ions have been observed to show an accelerating effect on the rate of oxidation of hexacyanoferrate(II)⁶, *p*-cresol⁷ and methyl aryl sulphides⁸. Based on the above results, the reaction mechanism for the oxidation of propanaldehyde and butanaldehyde, showing identical kinetics, may be described as given below,

where R' is C₂H₅ (in propanaldehyde) and C₃H₇ (in butanaldehyde).

The total [Ru^{III}] may be written as

$$[Ru^{III}]_T = [Cl^-] + [C_2] + [X] \quad (5)$$

The value of [X] may be determined on solving equation (5) in terms of [X] with the help of steps (ii) and (iii) and may be written as equation (6) with a reasonable assumption that $1 \gg K_3 [BAT]$,

$$[X] = \frac{K_2 K_3 [Ru^{III}]_T [BAT] [H_2O]}{[Cl^-] + K_2 [H_2O]} \quad (6)$$

Considering stoichiometric data, the rate of reaction as measured by the consumption of bromamine-T is given by equation (7),

$$\frac{-d[BAT]}{dt} = k_d [X] [R'CHO] \quad (7)$$

The final rate law may be written considering step (i) and equations (6) and (7).

$$\frac{-d[BAT]}{dt} = \frac{k [BAT] [Aldehyde] [Ru^{III}]_T [H^+]}{K_2 [H_2O] + [Cl^-]} \quad (8)$$

where $k = k_d K_1 K_2 K_3 [H_2O]$. The rate law (8) is in complete agreement with our kinetic observations and accords well with stoichiometry, negligible effect of ionic strength of the medium, insignificant effect of *p*-toluene sulphonamide. The high negative values of entropy of activation suggest that the degree of freedom of transition state complex is less than the degree of freedom of reacting molecules. Since the rate law (8) is derived on the basis of the suggested mechanism, it accords well with activation parameters.

Structure of the complex formed in step (iii) is not known but in order to account for its hydride ion abstracting capacity, a cyclic structure can be assigned,

It is clear from the structure that the electron density around the nitrogen atom in *N*-bromotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide is decreased and N-Br bond becomes weaker subsequently. The electrophilic character and, therefore, the hydride ion abstracting capacity of *N*-bromotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide is increased after complexation resulting in an interaction with the aldehyde. Freeman and Scott⁹ also suggested that the oxidation of mandelic acid by the alkaline permanganate proceeds either by a hydride ion transfer or a hydrogen atom abstraction from the mandelate dianion by permanganate and thus support the above mechanism.

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